

Recyclability of Recycled Concrete Products in Cements

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The Circular Economy not only implies the recycling of waste to obtain secondary raw materials that can be used in new products, but also to the eventual disposal of the wastes coming from the end-of-life of this recycled products. Thus, the design of the recycled products should focus the very end of these products and their recycling opportunities.

About 500 million tons of CDW are generated annually in the EU. CDW is one of the priority waste streams in the EU, with a target of 70% recycling by 2020 set in the Waste Framework Directive. That means that when the target is reached, Europe will produce 350 million tons of recycled products. How to recycle these recycled products will turn into a major issue.

This research addresses the recycling possibilities of a concrete product that contains coarse concrete aggregate as recycled material. The use of this finely milled product is proposed as an active addition to cement that already includes by-products in their composition.

The partial substitution of cement by secondary raw materials contributes positively to the reduction of waste dumping and to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions. However, the substitution rates of secondary raw materials are higher in concrete aggregates (20%) than in cements. The dosage of a concrete includes approximately three times more coarse aggregate than cement. This means that the amount of waste that can be incorporated into recycled concrete is greater if it is done as coarse aggregate than if it is added to cement. The main advantage of the partial substitution of cement lies in the reduction of CO₂ derived from the decarbonization process of the cement raw materials.

Initially, small proportions of substitution of the milled concrete by cement (5, 7 and 10 %) are planned with the aim to assess the potential advantages of its use, the impact of the substitution on the technical requirements of the product application and the potential limitations that must be imposed for an adequate use of the new eco-cement.

These small substitutions can cause a reduction in CO₂ production related to the decarbonation of calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) as a raw material for cement. Initially, this reduction is estimated to nearly 38-76 kg of CO₂ per ton of produced cement. On the other hand, it is recommended to propose a test plan that determines the dosage limits for the additions according to their impact on the mechanical behavior of the new products, and consequently a test plan has been designed and it is suggested to define the concrete additions.

Keywords: circular economy, cement, concrete, recycling

Acknowledgment

The authors thank the Fundación Gómez Pardo for its support to the research and development of this publication.

This article has been partially funded by Cinderela project which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation Programme under grant agreement N°776751.

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support from the Slovenian Research Agency (PhD

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